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REVISITING THE PROBLEM OF STAFFING THE SYSTEM OF THE PRIMARY MEDICAL CARE IN UKRAINE

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Summary. Shafransky V. V., Slabky G. O. **REVISITING THE PROBLEM OF STAFFING THE SYSTEM OF THE PRIMARY MEDICAL CARE IN UKRAINE.** The analysis of availability of primary health care institutions in the regions of Ukraine and provision of the population with the positions of doctors of general practice - family doctors, the availability of these positions and the level of their staffing is presented. The availability of positions of junior specialists with medical education at rural health posts (RHP) and their level of staffing is analyzed as well. The low level of staffing of general practitioners-family doctors with a reliable difference of this indicator by region is shown. It was noted that this situation reason is the lack of motivation in medical workers.

Key words: primary health care, priority development, medical personnel, staffing level.

Реферат. Шафранский В. В.¹, Слабкий Г. О.² **К ВОПРОСУ КАДРОВОГО ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ СИСТЕМЫ ПЕРВИЧНОЙ МЕДИКО-САНИТАРНОЙ ПОМОЩИ В УКРАИНЕ** - ¹Национальный медицинский университет им. А. А. Богомольца; ²Ужгородський національний університет. Развитие первичной медико-санитарной помощи (ПМСП) на принципах общей врачебной практики-семейной медицины является приоритетным направлением реформы здравоохранения в Украине. Отработка современной модели ПМСП проводилось в пилотных регионах Винницкой, Днепропетровской, Донецкой областях и г. Киеве в 2012-2014 г. г. За время пилотного проекта была проведена структурная перестройка с разграничением первичного и вторичного уровней оказания медицинской помощи и формированием юридически самостоятельных центров ПМСП, а также внедрены современные механизмы финансирования. В пилотных регионах был отработан механизм свободного выбора населением семейного врача и законодательно ему предоставлено право определять медицинский маршрут пациента. Также был разработан и введен мотивационный механизм для обеспечения эффективной и качественной работы медицинскими работниками первичного звена, особенно профилактического. При этом особое внимание уделяется кадровой политике. **Цель:** изучить и проанализировать состояние кадрового обеспечения системы первичной медико-санитарной помощи в Украине. **Материалами** исследования стали данные отраслевой статистической отчетности за период 2013-2016 г. г. При выполнении исследования использованы статистический и библиосемантический методы. **Результаты и выводы.** В результате проведенного исследования показан низкий уровень укомплектованности должностей врачей общей практики - семейных врачей с достоверной разницей показателя в разрезе регионов. Отмечено, что причиной данного состояния кадрового обеспечения первичного звена медико-санитарной помощи является отсутствие мотивации медицинских работников к работе именно на первичном уровне медицинской помощи.

Ключевые слова: общая врачебная практика, семейная медицина, кадровое обеспечение, мотивация медицинских работников.

Реферат. Шафранский В. В.¹, Слабкий Г. О.² **ДО ПИТАННЯ КАДРОВОГО ЗАБЕЗПЕЧЕННЯ СИСТЕМИ ПЕРВИННОЇ МЕДИКО-САНІТАРНОЇ ДОПОМОГИ В УКРАЇНІ** - ¹Національний медичний університет ім. О. О. Богомольця; ²Ужгородський національний університет. Розвиток первинної медико-санітарної допомоги (ПМСД) на засадах загальної лікарської практики-сімейної медицини є пріоритетним напрямком реформи охорони здоров'я в Україні. Відпрацювання сучасної моделі ПМСД проводилося в пілотних регіонах Вінницькій, Дніпропетровській, Донецькій областях та м. Києві в 2012-2014 р. р. За час пілотного проєкту було проведено структурну перебудову з розмежуванням первинного та вторинного рівнів надання медичної допомоги та формуванням юридично самостійних Центрів ПМСД і запроваджено сучасні механізми фінансування. В пілотних регіонах було відпрацьовано механізм вільного вибору населенням сімейного лікаря та законодавчо надано йому право визначати медичний маршрут пацієнта. Також було розроблено та запроваджено мотиваційні механізми для забезпечення ефективної та якісної праці медичними працівниками первинної ланки, особливо профілактичної. При цьому надзвичайно важлива увага приділяється кадровій політиці. **Мета:** вивчити та проаналізувати стан кадрового забезпечення системи первинної медико-санітарної допомоги в Україні. **Матеріалами** дослідження стали дані галузевої статистичної звітності за період 2013-2016 р. р. При виконанні дослідження використано статистичний та бібліосемантичний методи. **Результати та висновки.** В результаті дослідження, що проведено показано низький рівень укомплектованості посад лікарів загальної практики-сімейних лікарів з достовірною різницею показника в розрізі регіонів. Відмічено, що причиною даного стану кадрового забезпечення первинної ланки медико-санітарної допомоги є відсутність мотивації медичних працівників до роботи саме на первинному рівні медичної допомоги.

Ключові слова: загальна лікарська практика, сімейна медицина, кадрове забезпечення, мотивація медичних працівників.

In Ukraine health care reform is being implemented [10], its priority direction is the development of primary medical and sanitary care (PMSC) on the basis of general medical practice - family medicine [2, 6]. Perfection of modern PMSC model was carried out in pilot regions by health system reform in the country - Vinnytsia, Dnipropetrovsk, Donetsk regions and Kyiv in 2012-2014 [8]. During the pilot project, a structural reorganization was conducted with the distinction between primary and secondary levels of medical care provision and the formation of legally independent centers of primary medical care [11, 12] and modern financing mechanisms [4] were introduced. In the pilot regions the mechanism of free choice of the family doctor [13] was worked out and the doctor was legally granted the right to determine the medical route of the patient [7]. Motivational mechanisms have also been developed and introduced to provide effective and quality work for primary care professionals, especially for preventive care [5, 9]. In this case special attention was paid to human resources policy [1, 3].

The objective: To study and analyze the state of staffing of the primary medical care system in Ukraine.

Materials and methods. The materials of the study were the data of sector statistical reporting for 2013-2016. In the course of the study statistical and bibliosemantic methods were used.

Results and discussion

In 2016, the development of primary health care on the basis of family medicine remained a priority in the process of reforming the health care sector in Ukraine. The urgent task of optimizing the primary health care activities was to provide the population with affordable and quality primary health care. This can be achieved through further development of the PMSC's network and the provision of primary care facilities by qualified medical personnel.

The development of primary health care in Ukraine in 2016 from the above positions has been analyzed.

Table 1 provides data on the number of PMSC centers in the regions of Ukraine and the availability of medical outpatient clinics and rural health posts (RHPs).

Table 1

Centers of primary medical and sanitary care and their structure, 2016

Administrative territories	Independent Centers of PMSC	Including rural administrative districts	In the structure of independent centers of PMSC	
			Outpatient clinics	RHPs
Ukraine	616	445	5233	11177
Vinitsa Region	34	28	325	837
Volyn Region	20	15	138	758
Dnepropetrovsk Region	54	23	418	392
Donetsk Region	33	11	247	325
Zhitomir Region	26	24	214	688
Transcarpathian Region	13	11	232	235
Zaporozhiye Region	38	27	277	357
Ivano-Frankovsk Region	5	5	56	119
Kiev Region	29	24	292	618
Kirovograd Region	24	20	162	475
Lugaansk region	16	12	128	236
Lviv Region	4	4	28	111
Mykolayev Region	28	19	220	381
Odesa Region	40	26	279	450
Poltava Region	34	26	328	618
Rivno Region	22	18	166	614
Sumy Region	19	15	112	341
Ternopol Region	16	15	203	650
Kharkiv Region	33	31	332	496
Kherson Region	20	19	159	342
Khmelnitsk Region	23	22	212	887
Cherkasy Region	18	15	127	380
Chernovtsy Region	14	12	168	205
Chernigov Region	25	23	153	662
Kiev	28		257	

In Ukraine, the network of PMSC Centers is practically completely formed as legally independent health care institutions. In total, 616 PMSC Centers function in the country, out of which 445 (72.2%) operate in rural areas. In the structure of the centers operate 5233 outpatient clinics and 11177 RHPs.

In the context of the regions, the number of PMSC centers and the established medical clinics and RHPs depends on the population size, its settlement, which determines the administrative-territorial structure of the region, the level of development of primary health care on the basis of general medical practice - family medicine in the region. Thus, the largest number of PMSC centers was formed in Dnipropetrovsk region (54), and the smallest in Lviv (4) and Ivano-Frankivsk (5) regions.

One of the indicators that determines the availability of primary health care is the presence of the medical outpatient clinics in the structure of PMSC's centers. The largest number of outpatient clinics is in the Dnipropetrovsk region (418), Kharkiv (332) and Poltava (328) regions, and the smallest in the Lviv (28) and Ivano-Frankivsk (56) regions.

The largest number of RHPs operates in Vinnytsia (837), Volyn (756) and Zhytomyr (688)

regions.

Further, data on the availability of GPs - family doctors positions and their employment in 2016 were studied. The results obtained are presented in Table 2

Table 2

The positions of general practitioners - family doctors and their employment in 2016

Administrative territories	Full-time job	Filled vacancy	Physical persons at the filled vacancies	Difference between full-time jobs and filled vacancies	Difference between full-time jobs and physical persons	% Staffing level of full-time jobs + secondary job	% Staffing level of full-time post with physical persons
Ukraine	18719.25	15 976.75	13696	2 742.50	5 023.25	85.35	73.17
Vinitsa Region	1 143.50	920.75	819	222.75	324.50	80.52	71.62
Volyn Region	504.25	452.00	384	52.25	120.25	89.64	76.15
Dnepropetrovsk Region	1 821.75	1 597.25	1350	224.50	471.75	87.68	74.10
Donetsk Region	816.00	612.50	510	203.50	306.00	75.06	62.50
Zhitomir Region	775.00	685.25	561	89.75	214.00	88.42	72.39
Transcarpathian Region	713.00	665.75	637	47.25	76.00	93.37	89.34
Zaporozhiye Region	855.00	744.00	623	111.00	232.00	87.02	72.87
Ivano-Frankovsk Region	464.75	425.25	400	39.50	64.75	91.50	86.07
Kiev Region	836.00	703.50	592	132.50	244.00	84.15	70.81
Kirovograd Region	426.50	325.25	253	101.25	173.50	76.26	59.32
Lugaansk region	229.50	179.25	150	50.25	79.50	78.10	65.36
Lviv Region	994.50	963.25	921	31.25	73.50	96.86	92.61
Mykolayev Region	600.00	474.50	377	125.50	223.00	79.08	62.83
Odesa Region	1 453.25	1 156.50	981	296.75	472.25	79.58	67.50
Poltava Region	892.00	720.50	598	171.50	294.00	80.77	67.04
Rivno Region	412.25	377.50	339	34.75	73.25	91.57	82.23
Sumy Region	427.00	377.50	320	49.50	107.00	88.41	74.94
Ternopol Region	645.50	568.75	529	76.75	116.50	88.11	81.95
Kharkiv Region	1 001.00	863.75	716	137.25	285.00	86.29	71.53
Kherson Region	417.25	305.75	224	111.50	193.25	73.28	53.68
Khmelnitsk Region	603.25	535.50	480	67.75	123.25	88.77	79.57
Cherkasy Region	598.00	503.00	398	95.00	200.00	84.11	66.56
Chernovtsy Region	480.25	443.00	374	37.25	106.25	92.24	77.88
Chernigov Region	478.00	395.50	321	82.50	157.00	82.74	67.15
Kiev	1 131.75	981.00	839	150.75	292.75	86.68	74.13

In 2016, the Ministry of Health of Ukraine introduced 1871925 posts of general practitioners - family doctors, of which 1597675 are employed with 13696 physical persons of the given profile. At the same time, the level of staffing of full-time positions is only 85.35%, and the level of staffing posts by individuals is 73.17%. At the same time, in 16 (64.0%) regions, the level of staffing by individuals is less than 75%, which, according to evidence-based management, does not empower to render affordable and quality primary health care for the entire population. The lowest is the level of staffing by individuals in the following regions: Kherson (53.68%), Kirovograd (59.32%), Donetsk (62.50%), Mykolaiv region (62.83%). In Kyiv, the level of staffing of staff posts by individuals is 74.13%.

The following is the staffing level per 10 000 people by general practitioners-family doctors in the dynamics in 2013-2016 by regions.

Table 3

Staffing level by general practitioners - family doctors per 10 000 of general population

Administrative territories	Per 10 000 of general population			
	2013	2014	2015	2016
Україна	2.67	2.89	3.13	3.40
Vinitsa Region	4.62	5.19	5.50	5.61
Volyn Region	2.70	3.02	3.40	3.78
Dnepropetrovsk Region	3.09	3.81	4.05	4.25
Donetsk Region	2.00	1.08	2.56	2.65
Zhitomir Region	4.07	4.27	4.46	4.72
Transcarpathian Region	4.54	4.68	4.82	5.07
Zaporozhiye Region	2.32	2.93	3.10	4.03
Ivano-Frankovsk Region	1.99	2.67	3.02	3.33
Kiev Region	2.02	2.46	3.02	3.38
Kirovograd Region	1.75	1.63	2.06	2.73
Lugaansk Region	1.16	0.60	2.11	2.23
Lviv Region	2.87	3.11	3.34	3.88
Mykolayev Region	2.25	2.74	3.08	3.38
Odessa Region	3.32	3.81	3.98	4.32
Poltava Region	3.96	4.02	4.13	4.33
Rivno Region	1.78	2.03	2.47	3.10
Sumy Region	2.17	2.42	2.53	2.97
Ternopol Region	4.81	5.00	5.19	5.28
Kharkiv Region	2.66	2.68	2.72	2.85
Kherson Region	1.43	1.65	1.93	2.22
Khmelnitsk Region	2.71	3.13	3.61	3.88
Cherkasy Region	2.73	2.87	3.18	3.32
Chernovtsy Region	4.90	5.14	5.18	5.17
Chernigov Region	2.31	2.62	3.09	3.22
Kiev	1.96	2.56	2.95	3.21

During this period there was an increase in the index of general population provision by

GP's - family doctors in Ukraine from 2.67 in 2013 to 3.40 in 2016 in all regions of the country. This indicator has significant differences.

Despite the positive dynamics in 2012-2016, the staffing level of primary health care link by GPs - family doctors, a significant number of rural medical outpatient clinics with nonreplaced by a physician (main worker) posts are registered. Table 4.

Table 4

**The number of rural medical clinics with nonreplaced positions of a doctor
(the main worker)**

Administrative territories	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Ukraine	374	489	386	380	484
Vinitza Region		-	--	-	-
Volyn Region	5	12	12	8	9
Dnepropetrovsk Region	32	39	38	38	39
Donetsk	19	3	12	11	93
Zhitomir Region	28	22	17	15	19
Transcarpathian Region	6	12	16	14	6
Zaporozhiye Region	27	25	14	14	14
Ivano-Frankovsk Region	-	--	-	-	1
Kiev Region	7	7	30	28	22
Kirovograd Region	23	17	17	15	15
Lugaansk Region	11	10	-	-	-
Lviv Region	10	9	3	5	6
Mykolayev Region	35	35	34	29	21
Odessa Region	31	31	26	27	32
Poltava Region	15	58	51	62	66
Rivno Region	11	3	-	-	-
Sumy Region	8	30	36	26	32
Ternopol Region	6	7	2	9	7
Kharkiv Region	-	100	21	22	33
Kherson Region	14	14	14	12	25
Khmelnitsk Region	14	20	18	20	21
Cherkasy Region	18	33	25	25	23
Chernovtsy Region	-	-	-	-	-
Chernigov Region	47	-	-	-	-

For the years under analysis in general the number of rural medical clinics with nonreplaced positions doctor's has some changes, but over the past three years it has a tendency to increase and in 2016 there were 484 outpatient clinics of such a type. In five regions such clinics are not registered. The largest number of such clinics exists in Donetsk (93), Poltava (66), Dnipropetrovsk (39), Kharkiv (33) and Odesa (32) regions. It should be noted that in the regional centers of these regions there are higher medical education institutions of the IV level of accreditation.

Below we present, in the terms of the regions, data on the number of RHPs and their staffing level by junior specialists with medical education. Table 5.

Table 5

Number of rural health posts and their staffing with junior specialists with medical education (including independent institutions, structural and separated structural units) in 2016

Адміністративні території	Число ФАПів всього	В т. ч. В складі ЦПМСД	Посади молодших спеціалістів з медичною освітою		Фізичні особи на зайнятих посадах	Укомплектованість штатних посад зайнятими (%)	Укомплектованість штатних посад фіз. Особами (%)	Число ФАПів без середнього медперсоналу
			штатні	зайняті				
Україна	13133	11177	15632,00	14468,25	14 478	92,6	92,6	736
Вінницька	838	837	1049,25	958,50	989	91,4	94,3	34
Волинська	758	758	917,00	890,25	892	97,1	97,3	29
Дніпропетровська	392	392	444,75	395,00	386	88,8	86,8	46
Донецька	325	325	367,50	310,00	287	84,4	78,1	49
Житомирська	804	688	886,00	828,50	822	93,5	92,8	20
Закарпатська	285	235	356,50	325,25	341	91,2	95,7	8
Запорізька	357	357	447,50	390,75	380	87,3	84,9	-
Івано-Франківська	529	119	787,50	770,50	801	97,8	101,7	-
Київська	639	618	801,25	656,75	598	82,0	74,6	70
Кіровоградська	475	475	552,25	508,75	486	92,1	88,0	23
Луганська	236	236	257,25	227,00	222	88,2	86,3	27
Львівська	996	111	1157,75	1133,50	1 179	97,9	101,8	9
Миколаївська	381	381	400,75	335,25	327	83,7	81,6	44
Одеська	507	450	678,25	598,50	596	88,2	87,9	52
Полтавська	618	618	660,50	612,25	624	92,7	94,5	57
Рівненська	620	614	776,00	757,00	798	97,6	102,8	5
Сумська	499	341	559,00	519,50	524	92,9	93,7	63
Тернопільська	734	650	895,00	854,50	868	95,5	97,0	13
Харківська	496	496	531,75	494,25	482	93,0	90,6	24
Херсонська	348	342	434,75	389,75	351	89,7	80,7	19
Хмельницька	887	887	1020,25	976,25	982	95,7	96,3	41
Черкаська	536	380	640,50	600,75	601	93,8	93,8	47
Чернівецька	211	205	279,50	267,50	273	95,7	97,7	-
Чернігівська	662	662	731,25	668,00	669	91,4	91,5	56

In 2016 there were 13133 RHPs of which 11177 were in the structure of PMSC centers. There was a higher level of staffing by full-time jobs at RHPs than in rural outpatient clinics. But at the same time a significant number of RHPs without the mid-level health professionals is registered. The number of RHPs without any medical worker is 736, which makes it impossible for the rural population to receive timely medical care.

The largest number of such RHPs is registered in Kyiv (70), Sumy (63), Poltava (57), Chernihiv (56), Odesa (52) and Donetsk (49) regions.

The reason for the low staffing by primary link care workers, especially in the countryside, is the lack of housing, the actual non-standardization of working time and low wages.

Conclusions

The analysis of existence of primary health care institutions in the regions of Ukraine and provision of the population with the positions of doctors of general practice - family doctors, the availability of these positions and the level of their staffing is presented. The availability of positions of junior specialists with medical education at RHPs and their level of staffing is also analyzed. The low level of staffing of general practitioners-family doctors with a reliable difference in the indicator by regions is shown. It was noted that the reason for this situation with personnel provision of primary health care link is the lack of motivation of medical workers to work at this particular level of medical care.

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